

PROBLEMS OF EPONYMY IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation: This article covers the problems of eponymy in modern linguistics, including the inability of eponyms to be removed from medicine, the role of eponyms in the creation of medical practical, scientific terminology, another problem associated with eponyms, whether or not to include them in paradigmatic relations, the problem of transcription in eponymy, the fact that eponyms based on the same name do not mean pointing to.

Keywords: lexicographic sources, synonymy in eponyms, antonymy, homonym phenomenon, eponymy, adverbial word and adjective compound form eponymy, medical eponyms, lexical-semantic system.

To date, the following work has been carried out on the study of eponyms: conditions have been identified that served as the basis for the formation of eponyms. The distribution of eponymy terms according to their belonging to the main clinical departments of Medicine was carried out, and annotations were made of the presented distribution; its necessary conditions were indicated; qualitative and quantitative characteristics were determined. Eponym names of diseases and their symptoms (a disease that occurs under the influence of a complex of external and internal factors) were studied. In clinical nomenclature, an analysis of nominative models of the formation of nominative pronouns and their quantitative accounting was carried out. The advantages and disadvantages of using atonymic terms were evaluated and the role of. Eponymic terms in medical science and practice was determined.

In medical practice, observations were made and the features of the appearance of the names of the symptoms of the disease were analyzed. Symptoms, reflexes, tests, laws, phenomena, as well as symptom complexes, syndromes and diseases, depending on the nationality, historical, cultural and economic characteristics of their authors, the foundations of the formation of names of treatment methods, tests, medical objects, etc. discovered by scientists were studied.

In the construction of modern medical nomenclature, some cognate terms have been dropped or replaced with names that reflect the structural, functional and topographic characteristics of the designated object. On the one hand, such an approach can be fully explained by the need to unify the terminological

system. However, it seems to us that the terms of the same name cannot be excluded from the science and practice of Medicine. It is wrong and unfair. Because, they enrich the speech of a specialist, bring color to scientific research and publications. The interest of young specialists in scientific research increases.

There are still issues in the field that cannot find a solution without looking at the many scientific studies and achievements that have been made like this. Even the problems that are causing controversy among many scientists around the world today are not missing. In contrast to the purpose of our study, we also tried to find solutions to some of these issues.

The purpose of this work is to classify the proverbial terms recorded in lexicographic sources, determine the features of their application in various subsystems of the medical dictionary and determine the place of eponyms in the creation of medical practical, scientific terminology. It consists of using special dictionaries as sources of Material and providing information dedicated to the problem of systematizing and characterizing medical terms that represent the most complete set of names of symptoms and syndromes.

To regulate the inclusion of eponyms in various terminological systems, scientists propose to determine some general conditions. Compliance with them will help to receive reasonable nominations. These conditions include:

1. World recognition of the personal services of a person whose name is given for a period of time.

2. Direct authorship or connection of the works of a famous person with the subject of the title.

3. Determination of the significance of the author's name in the proposed object.

4. Priority of the proposal for the introduction of the term.

5. Disorientation or absence of dissonant associations.

There has been debate among scientists as to what is the maximum number of components terminological compounds should be included in their composition. S. in this regard. V. According to grinev's terminological compounds, 7-component terms define the limit of the lexical size of the term. Because it is directly related to the amount of memory and the limited number of units of information that a person can absorb at the same time," he believes. In addition, B.N. Golovin and R.Y. Even if cobrins believe that terminological compounds can contain ten or more components, some researchers categorically deny this. In Particular, S.D. According to shelov's comments in this regard, there cannot be

such a structured term, because “...any lexical boundaries must be defined, for example, three, five, even seven-component. In fact, the term should not be either long or short,” says the researcher. Hence, the term should, above all, convey the content of the concept as correctly as possible, reflect the peculiarities, as well as the connections with other concepts in the system, regardless of the number of components it contains.

It should be remembered that in the expression of individual names of objects and processes in the life of society, including in scientific life, eponyms in most cases lose the quality of individual designation. For example, not everyone can remember the eternal mistress of spring and gardens, the love and beauty of the Roman goddess - Venus, when using such units as venereological diseases, Venereology, Veterinary Medicine. Or, the German scientist V.K. Not everyone remembers X-ray's discovery of radioactive radiation when using the name of the radiation X-ray unit and dozens of terms related to medical processes and equipment. It can be said that when a slot of words and phrases is made, the original eponym is often forgotten. This word is also forgotten when it turns from a proverbial horse to a common horse.

Another problem with eponyms as a lexical unit is the question of whether or not to include them in paradigmatic relationships. There are peat views and feedback on this issue. N.V. Novinskaya argued that eponyms could enter into synonymy, antonymy, polysemy, and omonymy relations. While the term terminological compounds is about these units are not characteristic of polysemia and antonymia, olima believes. However, S.G. Kazarina does not quite agree with this conclusion. In his opinion, the study of eponyms in medical terminology allows the author to describe these compounds with both antonymy and polysemy, but they are represented by an unnamed dictionary. At this point, it should be said that the idea that eponyms are far from synonymous does not justify much. Let's look at this through the following examples:

Eponyms denoting a concept can be made from different specific names in different countries. For example, “cashew disease” and “Wake disease” are used to mean “childhood endemic disease”.

In the use of eponyms in scientific terminology, the following difficulties may arise: eponyms based on the same name do not mean referring to a single doctor. This condition can lead to some cultural confusion. For example, the “Pik cell,” Pik “disease,” Pik “pericarditis” are named in honor of (German patalog Louis Pik), (Czech psychiatrist Arnold Pik), and (Australian physician Friedel Pik) respectively.

Eponyms based on the names of doctors of another country can be very difficult to read and write for those who do not speak this language. For example, "Kuntscher "symptom," Hirschsprung "disease," Papanikolaou " syndrome, etc. At the same time, one of the main problems of domestic and foreign lexicology can be distinguished. While eponymic terms are included in the dictionary Corpus, they are often not represented by phonetic symbols, i.e. transcription. This makes their use in oral professional speech very difficult.

In solving the problem of generating an eponymic term, N.V.Novinskaya touches on the semantics of names, the main methods and models for making eponym terms: "an integral component of Eponymic terms – the problem of semantics are specific names, which are one of the most complex issues. Are controversial problems that arise in relation to the study of the named dictionary" . The scientist identifies the following as the main methods of forming eponymic names:

- 1) semantic;
- 2) morphological;
- 3) syntactic

The most studied category of eponyms in terms of semantics turned out to be eponyms of Medicine and anatomy. This can be explained by the fact that for the first time for users of a special dictionary, it is interesting who discovered various diseases, studied and began to treat the disease.

Despite such problems, eponymic terms are an integral part of the medical terminology of different languages, helping to shape scientific discourse. Eponyms as part of the language of science contribute to a deeper understanding of human activity and its culture

The problem of the cultural role of eponyms in the history of civilization is one of the issues worthy of special consideration. This problem can be found in many articles, including V.A.Vinogradov and N.V.Vasilyeva's dictionaries were also raised, and a number of other domestic and foreign scholars paid special attention to the cultural aspect of eponyms when studying nominative units. But even so, the matter is not yet as far as it can find its answer. This assumes that scientists in the field should conduct research on the same issue. The problem of lexicographic reflection of eponyms is relevant for the present.

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